

**ELECTRONIC GOVERNMENT IS A MEANS OF INCREASING THE
EFFICIENCY OF STATE ADMINISTRATION AND STRENGTHENING
PUBLIC CONTROL OVER IT**

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Today, it is recognized that all developed countries in the world have achieved their development due to the efficiency of public administration. Effectiveness in public administration largely depends on the formation and service of electronic government.

For the first time when Bill Clinton was President of the USA, the category of "e-government" was used as a concept related to the field of administrative management, reflecting the meaning of the development of Internet and information technologies and the use of these tools in public administration.

In our republic, the concept of "electronic government" both from a scientific point of view and from a legal point of view"[1] is aimed at ensuring the activities of state bodies in providing public services to individuals and legal entities by applying information and communication technologies, as well as electronic cooperation between departments shall be used in the sense of the system of organizational and legal measures and technical means.

The scope of this concept, which is widely used on a global scale, is somewhat wide, and its content acquires a multi-valued meaning. Today's international legal issues, in particular, in the decisions of the European courts on human rights, the concept of government is considered as a political institution with a unified system that includes legislative, executive and judicial authorities together with the central government apparatus[2].

Based on this, the concept of e-government is interpreted as a method of providing information and services through the Internet and ensuring the delivery of information and services to the general public. In this sense, the concept of electronic government is not an independent subject of government activity, but a form or method of implementation of the same activity.

Summarizing the above analysis, in simpler words, electronic government means the management process, in particular, the implementation of state management in electronic form. Due to the fact that the English concept of government is translated into Uzbek in the sense of government or state power management[3], the concept of electronic government, which refers to the electronic form of state management, is also included in scientific and legal usage in the form of electronic government, not electronic management[4].

Usually, e-government refers to "electronic state", "electronic state and its apparatus", "electronic infrastructure", "state in the information society" and the phenomenon of society that is becoming more informational and has its own, unprecedented aspects[5].

Based on the above reasoning, it can be said that the concept of "electronic government" in the Uzbek language does not fully match the English electronic government category used at the international level. This can also be explained by the fact that people who do not have enough ideas about the concept of electronic government, when they first encounter the same concept, describe the signs that are not part of its content as features specific to this category[6].

If we pay attention to the transformation of the concept of electronic government from the first periods of scientific use to the present day, it can be observed that it has undergone many changes in terms of volume and content under the influence of various factors. This can be explained by factors such as the fact that the same phenomenon has been studied as a subject of different fields, even interdisciplinary research, and, moreover, it is applied in the management processes of different countries based on local characteristics. Interpretations of the concept of "electronic government" defined from the point of view of improving the efficiency of public administration may seem more perfect than its interpretations in the "technological" sense. But the relative completeness of this approach does not mean that it covers all aspects related to e-government. Based on this, it can be said that the development of a relatively comprehensive definition of the concept of electronic government depends on the level of application of information technology capabilities in society.

In Uzbekistan, where electronic government is increasingly being implemented, it is considered as a means of increasing the efficiency of public administration and strengthening public control over it, using the possibilities of information technologies. However, the approaches to the definition of the concept of electronic government show that there are various ideas related to its understanding, and there are even ideas that promote the inappropriateness of calling this phenomenon by the same name "electronic government". In particular, in many definitions in this regard, e-government is described as a means of increasing the efficiency of public administration, relying on the capabilities of information technologies. For example, according to Andrey Korotkov, the head of the Russian government information department, "this (e-government) is a vague term, we are not talking about e-government, but about the government that uses information technology services, the Federal

assemblies that use information technology ", we need to talk about Courts using information technologies, and in general, the state and civil society structures, as well as businessmen, about the communicative environment that allows them to understand each other and communicate on the basis of a single standard"[7]. Ayni o'rinda yuqorida ham aytilganidek, elektron hukumat real hukumat bilan ayniy bo'lgan uning vertual shakli emas, balki davlat boshqaruvini amalga oshirishning zamonaviy vositalaridan biri sifatida talqin qilinmoqda. Shu ma'noda, bunday yondashuvlarda elektron hukumat tushunchasining o'rniga davlat boshqaruvini elektronlashtirish atamasini qo'llash taklif qilinadi.

At the same time, as mentioned above, e-government is interpreted not as its vertual form, which is the same as real government, but as one of the modern means of implementing public administration. In this sense, in such approaches, instead of the concept of e-government, it is proposed to use the term electronization of Public Administration. In general, in such approaches, e-government does not imply a radical transformation of the structures of the existing state administration apparatus, in other words, a reorganization, but modernization based on the capabilities of information technologies.

In order for this system to exchange information, allow citizens to complete the necessary documents without leaving their homes, and allow public procurement to be carried out through open e-commerce portals, the databases of various state organizations should be coordinated and integrated with each other. The concept of "electronic government" is somewhat broad, and in a broad sense it means the implementation of effective public administration through modern computer and communication technologies. Despite the different interpretations of the concept of electronic government in scientific studies, it is a means of modernizing public administration, increasing the efficiency of government bodies, raising the interaction between the state and citizens to a new level of quality, stimulating economic development, and regulating social relations based on new mechanisms. functions. For example, the introduction of "electronic government" is related to factors such as the reform of the structures of state administration, in particular, changes in the amount and nature of the functions of state bodies, as well as the implementation of administrative electronic regulations on their activities.

Thus, e-government serves to describe the role of public administration bodies in the life of the state and society in the context of the information society based on a short and modern approach. This term includes new methods of

organization and development of public administration, as well as the development of new mechanisms for improving the system of communication with the people, radically updating the indicators of achieving useful results in a certain field of activity, reducing its low output and the responsibility of state bodies. takes E-government as a tool requires continuous application of targeted, coordinated new information technologies in the implementation of public administration functions, and as a result, it leads to strengthening of public control over state bodies.

It should be mentioned separately that the concept of electronic government is not considered an alternative form of government to traditional government, that is, electronic government means the transfer of traditional public administration to an efficient form. In simpler words, e-government is used in the field of traditional public administration, it is modern, fast, and brings a lot of results with the use of few resources. It is a technical, social, political and economic tool.

The launch of the Open Data Portal in 2015 was one of the important steps in the introduction of electronic government in the republic. At the initial stage, 80 types of information from 8 organizations were placed on it, at the beginning of 2017, 2216 types of information from 120 organizations were placed on this portal, and at the beginning of 2022, 13578 types of information from 181 organizations were placed on this portal[8]. This information applies to the economy, healthcare, education, transport and other relevant areas.

In addition, in accordance with the comprehensive program for the development of the National Information and Communication System of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2013-2020, it is planned to gradually develop the high-speed telecommunication infrastructure for the effective functioning of the electronic government. In particular, until 2020, 17 large projects were implemented to further expand the capacity of Internet channels and develop broadband networks, especially in remote regions. In addition, until 2020, 22 projects were launched to ensure and develop electronic communication of citizens with state bodies.

All the changes that are being implemented in Uzbekistan to improve the processes of introducing electronic government based on rational bureaucracy should be implemented on the basis of creating a unified system of electronic administrative regulations. It determines the procedures for the implementation of all processes that ensure the performance of state functions. This creates an opportunity for the government of the Republic of Uzbekistan to engage in

meaningful constructive dialogue with government organizations, citizens, and business representatives. In particular, the uniformity of regulations serves to increase transparency by imposing the same rights and obligations on both parties entering into dialogue without allowing for diversity of interpretations. On the other hand, it minimizes the human factor and leads to automatic implementation of all processes. This, in turn, can lead to the minimization of conflict of interests and the possibility of corruption.

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